

FEATURES OF TEACHING TECHNIQUES OF DISTANCE RUNNING IN TRACK AND FIELD ATHLETICS

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Annotation: In the system of various organizational forms, the physical education lesson occupies a special place, being the main form of physical education of the student and especially teaching the basics of athletics technique. The author found that the implementation of these tasks in teaching running is achieved by targeted content, proper organization and selection of the dosage of physical exercises, taking into account the health status, physical development, age and gender characteristics of students.

Key words: motor skills and skills, physical exercises, physical load, underwater exercises, athletics exercises, health promotion, physical development.

Introduction. In physical education classes when learning to run, students receive fairly complete knowledge of motor activity and acquire the necessary motor skills [1, 3, 4]. Thanks to athletics running, you can improve your ability to control your movements, make them fast and economical [2, 5]. The main objectives of conducting athletics classes are to further strengthen health, promote proper physical development and comprehensive training of students. When performing athletics exercises, almost all muscle groups of the body are strengthened, agility and endurance are developed [7, 8, 9]. Also, in the process of running, volitional qualities are developed, the ability to calculate one's strength and overcome obstacles is developed [6, 10, 11].

In order for students to successfully master the movements, underwater exercises are used. These may include exercises that reproduce the basic structure of

a motor action from which secondary elements and details are excluded [12, 14, 16]. The remaining underwater exercises help to practice individual elements of movements. These then form the main movement. Performing track and field exercises requires significant dynamic work of many muscle groups of the human body, has a significant training effect, and therefore can be used in numerous sports [13, 15, 17]. In addition to great health value, athletics exercises have a significant applied nature.

After mastering the basics of motor action, they begin to improve it. When choosing teaching methods, selecting physical exercises and dosing physical activity, it is necessary to take into account the developmental characteristics of the adolescent body. The process of growth and development of the body occurs continuously and at the same time unevenly: in certain age periods, the rate of increase in body mass and size, differentiation of tissues and organs is not the same [18, 19, 20]. In addition, in each age period the growth and development of individual organs and systems in relation to each other is also uneven.

Athletics is of great health importance, because exercises are mainly carried out in the fresh air, and most of the muscles of the body are involved in the exercises. Athletics exercises improve the activity of the musculoskeletal system, internal organs and body systems as a whole, B.B. Boborakhmatov notes in his publications. Also, athletics is one of the most accessible popular sports that combines natural physical exercises: walking, running, jumping, throwing. When doing track and field running, a variety of physical exercises affects the accuracy of load regulation, has important health benefits, and is also accessible to all age categories.

The constant increase in the flow of various educational information, extremely intense mental activity, lack of free time and physical inactivity progressing with each academic year are one of the main reasons for the decrease in physical performance and functional state of the body of students. The situation is aggravated by the fact that physical health does not rank first in the ranking of basic life values and success factors. This is what encourages the search for new ways to

organize physical development, helping to increase the motivation of students for physical education and sports activities.

The effect of physical exercises on a growing organism can be beneficial only when they are applied in accordance with the requirements and capabilities determined by the biological state of both the organism as a whole and its individual organs and systems. Movements that are difficult to coordinate are first broken down and taught in parts. First, they are combined several at a time and only after that they learn the movements as a whole.

In athletics lessons, you can show students the direct effects of athletics exercises on body functions, for example, a decrease in heart rate after systematic exercise.

Long running and systematic training help normalize body weight. Systematic running training increases the body's protective functions due to better regulation of heat exchange and the protective properties of the blood.

Systematic athletics exercises help train the cardiovascular system. Along with training the cardiovascular system, the body's ability to supply working muscles with oxygen improves. During intensive work, the delivery of additional oxygen and the timely release of metabolic products from the body in trained children occurs not only due to increased breathing, but also an increase in its depth.

Strengthening the health of students requires strict regulation of physical activity on the student's body throughout the lesson. It is necessary to gradually introduce the student's body into work, and also, after performing feasible physical activity, to bring it into a relatively calm state. In the system of various forms of physical education, closely interconnected, a special place is occupied by the physical education lesson, which is the main form of physical education of the student.

In slow running, the main task of teaching motor actions is mainly aimed at mastering vital motor actions and improving the ability to use actions in various complex conditions. The basic techniques for teaching motor actions remain the

same. This is the communication of theoretical information and the direct implementation of learning motor actions.

The main task is to teach all students to run freely, without tension, gradually increasing the distance. It is important to take into account the motor activity children will receive while learning to run. And also in learning to run, it is necessary to achieve free movements, while maintaining good posture and the correct form of all movements, as well as a wide and free step on the toes with an appropriate extension of the hip of the swing leg. The main features of a rational running technique are the ease and freedom of running movements performed with high amplitude and frequency.

Educational tasks are solved on the basis of mastering the complexes of motor skills and abilities available in the program. During the learning process, students develop basic motor qualities: speed, agility, and also, within the capabilities of the body of children of a certain age, strength and endurance.

Correct load adjustment requires special attention. It is necessary to plan and regulate it in each individual exercise, taking into account the health status of each student, their preparedness, and mastery of certain skills. During the lesson, the load increases in waves; it increases and decreases. The teacher must carefully monitor how individual students cope with a particular load. The load in the lesson is manifested by the intensity of the exercises and the volume.

It is very important to ensure that students maintain correct posture when performing athletics exercises. Much attention should be paid to learning proper breathing. It should be systematically explained and reminded that when running at a slow and medium pace, the inhalation should be long and full, and that before starting it is necessary to take several deep breaths and exhalations.

The first task is to teach children to take the correct starting positions. In this case, teaching the starting position is usually combined with performing the exercise as a whole. When the starting position is mastered to the fore, the second task comes forward - to master the directions of the main movements of this action.

For example, when running, you need to place your feet straight, extend the hip of the swing leg high, and fully straighten the pushing leg during pushing. Following this, a new task is put forward - to master the amplitude of movements. For example, extend the hip of the swing leg in a way that is appropriate for a given running speed. Almost immediately you need to set a task to do the action freely, without excessive tension that hinders movement. Then the task is set to perform actions at greater speed. For example, follow the correct technique when running at a slow, medium and finally fast pace.

Conclusions. Summarizing the main scientific sources, it has been established that the psychological characteristics of the character of children are very important for the sports improvement of those who engage in physical exercise and lead a healthy lifestyle. In physical education classes, students receive fairly complete knowledge of motor activity and acquire the necessary motor skills.

The effectiveness of teaching running and the basics of athletics technique to adolescents is determined by the systematic implementation of loads on the body during training, taking into account the age and gender characteristics of children. Mastering motor skills and exercises to develop motor qualities should present students with significant but feasible difficulties and obstacles. Physical education lessons are of great importance for developing the will of those involved. The degree of difficulty of tasks should vary depending on the individual characteristics of students of this age.

Prospects for further research are to study running and the basics of technique in athletics among adolescents, taking into account the level of their physical development, the organization of mutual testing, self-esteem and self-control during training.

Performing athletics exercises requires significant dynamic work of many muscle groups of the human body, has a significant training effect, and therefore can be used in numerous sports.

Therefore, regular athletic running is good for health and can be recommended for improving functional status, preventing diseases and improving the body's resistance to adverse environmental factors.

References:

1. Babarakhmatov, B. B. (2022). Role of the trainer in the psychological training of the athlete in outschool work on physical education and sport. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 2(106), 206-209.
2. Boborakhmatov, B. (2022). Initial training of young athletes in the conditions of a sport class. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(13), 70-74.
3. Boborakhmatov Bobir Buriyevich. (2023, February 28). Features of teaching short running techniques. Youth, science, education: Topical issues, achievements and innovations, Prague, Czech. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7700211>
4. Boboraxmatov, B. B. R. (2022). Yengil atletikachilar organizmiga iqlim omillarining ta'siri. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(9), 338-347.
5. Boborakhmatov, B. B. (2023). Psychological preparation of athletes-sprinters. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(6), 84-90.
6. Boborakhmatov, B. B. (2023). Pedagogical conditions for increasing the speed of running for short distances. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(3), 181-188.
7. Buriyevich, B. B. (2022). Role of the Trainer in the Psychological Training of the Athlete in Out-School Work on Physical Education and Sport. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 29–32.
8. Buriyevich, B. B. (2022). Improvement of Speed and Strength Abilities in Young Middle Distance Runners. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 661-664.
9. Buriyevich, B. B. (2022). Conditions for forming skills to perform a low start in short distance run. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 525-528.

10. Buriyevich, B. B. (2022). Features of the Training Process of Young Athletes at the Initial Stage of Preparation. *International Journal of Formal Education*, (9), 103-107.

11. Bo‘riyevich, B. B. (2023). O ‘zbekistonda yengil atletika sport turining rivojlanish bosqichlari. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 2(4), 210-217.

12. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Pedagogical methods of sports selection in boxing. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(9), 192-168.

13. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Study of volitional qualities of students of the faculty of sports activities. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(9), 139-144.

14. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Ways to solution problems of psychological control of preparation of young athletes. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(9), 120-126.

15. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Features of psychological preparation of young athletes. *World of Scientific news in Science*, 1(2), 44-49.

16. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2023). Integration of Physical and Spiritual Education in the Formation of Personality.

17. Ustoev, A. K., & Babarahmatov, B. B. (2020). Спорт ўйинларининг ташкилий асосларида кўп йиллик тайёрлов тизими. *Молодой ученый*, (21), 799-801.

18. Бабарахматов, Б. Б. (2020). Подготовка будущих учителей физической культуры к инновационной деятельности. *Матрица научного познания*, (6), 403-407.

19. Боборахматов, Б. (2023). Енгил атлетиканинг югуриш турлари бўйича кўп йиллик тизимли бошқариш педагогик технологияси. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук / Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(S/3), 227–233.

20. Боборахматов, Б. Б. (2023). Енгил атлетика дарс машғулотларда қўлланиладиган ҳаракатли ўйинлар. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 2(2), 143-149.